

CONTENT-AWARE REGION-OF-INTEREST CODING: PARADIGM PROPOSAL, STATE-OF-THE-ART REVIEW, AND VIABILITY ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel method for on-board satellite image compression: content-aware region-of-interest coding. The proposed approach is based on applying change detection using deep learning to autonomously identify and segment regions of interest in satellite images, focusing on areas that have likely experienced changes. Existing techniques with a similar concept include cloud detection, where cloudy regions in the image are discarded, and vessel detection, where only vessels are preserved. However, the proposed approach differs from those methods in that it aims to offer a generalized change detection solution that is not limited to detecting specific objects. Unlike traditional change detection methods, which require bi-temporal image pairs (images from the same location captured at different times), the presented technique is designed to perform change detection using only a single image as input.

This work is part of a project by the Institut d'Estudis Espacials de Catalunya to enable on-board data compression for small satellites. An introduction to the method, a review of current state-of-the-art developments, and the viability of its implementation and application are discussed.

Key words: image compression; lossy compression; change detection; region-of-interest coding; remote sensing.

1. INTRODUCTION

On-board image compression typically aims to reduce data entropy by applying transformation or value prediction techniques, followed by efficiently encoding the transformed values or residuals using entropy coding methods [1]. Most of these techniques do not consider the image content. However, by considering the content, it is possible to discard parts of the image that do not contain important information while preserving only the relevant regions, significantly reducing the amount of data that needs to be transmitted to the ground —e.g., cloud detection techniques [2].

In this paper, we present a novel technique, content-aware region-of-interest coding, which defines a step-by-step process to extract and compress only the relevant regions of an image while discarding those that —presumably— do not contain important information. This technique is based on the fact that not all parts of an image provide useful information. Just as human vision focuses on specific objects of interest within a scene [3], often overlooking the background, many applications require attention to only certain regions of an image, while other parts contribute little or no relevant information. In the context of remote sensing and in the proposed method presented in this paper, the regions of interest are those which might have changed or show differences from the previous satellite capture of the same location. For example, monitoring changes in urban areas, agricultural fields, or specific infrastructure might be of higher priority than vast areas of ocean or unchanging terrain. Based on this premise, a compression method that detects which regions might have changed, preserving and storing only those, is proposed to be developed and evaluated for its feasibility.

This approach to detect parts of the image that might contain recent changes closely resembles change detection techniques, where the two bi-temporal images (images taken at different times) are compared, and their differences are extracted [4]. In our proposed technique, we aim to perform a similar task to determine possible recent changes but without the use of a previously captured image.

To accomplish this, a preliminary analysis of state-of-the-art change detection and object detection techniques is conducted to investigate whether similar approaches exist and to explore potential deep learning architectures that could be applied to perform this novel task. A thorough investigation of existing change detection datasets is also performed to obtain data for training the model that will detect areas of an image that are likely to have changed.

In order to develop a concept, a simple implementation is described in detail. Finally, a series of evaluation metrics are presented to assess the compression capabilities of the model and facilitate a benchmark comparison with the performance of other lossy techniques.

In Figure 1, the development roadmap of this project is presented. The first two stages are discussed in this paper, alongside an introduction to the method's characterization.

Figure 1: Project timeline highlighting the current progress.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. First, a general description of the method and its applicability is presented in Section 2. In Section 3, a brief review of relevant papers from the state of the art are discussed. Section 4 proposes a possible proof-of-concept implementation description and metrics to evaluate the method. Finally, the conclusions are summarized in Section 5.

2. PROPOSAL

This section provides a description of the application of content-aware region-of-interest coding in the context of remote sensing image capture, offering an overview of the processes involved.

We define content-aware region-of-interest coding as a method involving a sequence of processes to handle satellite-captured images on-board. This approach can be described by the following steps, also depicted in Figure 2:

1. **Image capture:** optical capture of a specific location is performed by the satellite.
2. **Image segmentation:** regions of the image that might have changed are selected, and the rest is discarded.
3. **Encoding:** a suitable compression method is applied to the segmented image.
4. **Downlink transmission:** the compressed, segmented image is transmitted to the ground.
5. **Decoding:** the on-board compression is reverted to retrieve the original segmented image.
6. **Reconstruction (optional):** a reconstruction of the discarded parts of the image is performed using a previously captured image of the same location.

Image capture and downlink transmission are standard procedures in on-board data broadcasting and are therefore not specifically addressed by the proposed method. This paper focuses on defining the image segmentation and encoding processes.

The proposed segmentation solution is based on an artificial intelligence process that can autonomously identify and segment regions of interest (ROIs) [5] from satellite images, focusing on areas that have likely experienced changes. This change detection method relies on a deep learning model trained on the ground, with the capability to be executed on board. The innovation in this approach lies in its ability to perform change detection using only one image as input, in contrast to traditional change detection methods that require a pair of bi-temporal images. A successful implementation of the proposed technique is expected to significantly reduce the amount of data that needs to be stored and processed on-board, as there is no need to retain multiple images for comparison purposes and only certain parts of the image are stored. Moreover, in this scenario, alignment or co-registration operations [6], which are typically required in traditional change detection methods and are computationally expensive to perform on board, are not necessary. Once the image

Figure 2: Content-aware region-of-interest coding process steps.

containing only the relevant parts is transmitted back to Earth, a reconstruction of the original image can be obtained by using older imagery from the same location to fill the missing gaps [7].

The artificial intelligence model is trained using data from change detection datasets, which consist of pairs of images and a binary change map indicating the regions that differ between them. By using a single image and its corresponding change map, a deep neural network is trained to identify parts of images that typically change over time. This training can be further enhanced by creating new change detection datasets from available satellite imagery and applying change detection methods to generate the change maps. Once the AI model achieves a significant level of accuracy, allowing it to discard irrelevant parts of the images with minimal error in detecting important regions, the amount of data that needs to be stored, compressed, and transmitted is expected to be significantly reduced.

3. STATE OF THE ART

A comprehensive research study of the state of the art in on-board change detection has been conducted to understand current progress in the field and to guide the implementation of the proposed approach. A total of 60 papers were analyzed, covering the most relevant topics in this area. The literature review focused on remote sensing object detection, change detection surveys and specific methods, and the application of these technologies on board.

Key findings from the literature review revealed that no papers were found that perform change detection prediction using a single image, as opposed to two images, with one serving as a reference. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the specific objective of this project has not been addressed in the existing literature.

The review provided valuable insights for the project implementation approach and was divided into three main parts:

1. Remote sensing object detection: articles about on-board techniques for identifying clouds, vessels, and vehicles.
2. Change detection: a selection of relevant papers on change detection, including surveys, deep learning methods, and on-board techniques.
3. Other related techniques: papers covering techniques pertinent to change detection or on-board data transmission.

The analysis and synthesis of knowledge established a path forward for developing the AI model to detect image regions that may contain changes. The deep learning architecture is to be based on and tested using current object detection models, some of which have already proven successful in on-board object detection. Since the model will perform inference using only a single image as input, it will also be trained with just one image during the training phase. Change detection datasets are planned to be used as training data for the model, and state-of-the-art change detection methods can be employed to enhance the training dataset by generating new binary change maps from existing satellite imagery. A schema of this process is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Diagram of the training process, where *AI* serves as the deep learning model with a single image *I* as its input and a change map *M* as its label to predict. *I'* is an image from the same location as *I* that is used, employing change detection methods, to generate new change maps *M*.

It is crucial to train the model with the specific goal of minimizing false negatives—cases where relevant parts of the image, which may contain changes, are incorrectly discarded. To achieve this, the objective function should be tuned to heavily penalize false negatives.

The following subsections offer a brief overview of the most prominent techniques analyzed in relation to change detection and object detection, along with a curated collection of the most relevant available change detection datasets.

3.1. Relevant change detection methods

Three significant change detection papers are discussed below.

- **A Spatial-Temporal Attention-Based Method and a New Dataset for Remote Sensing Image Change Detection** [8] proposes a novel Siamese-based spatial-temporal attention neural network (STANet) for change detection, which models spatial-temporal relationships. They integrate a change detection self-attention module in the process of feature extraction. The authors also introduced a new dataset, LEVIR-CD, composed of pairs of bitemporal Google Earth images, which at the time of publication surpasses the largest existing change detection dataset.
- **Remote Sensing Image Change Detection With Transformers** [9] proposes a bitemporal image transformer (BIT) for change detection. The main idea presented is that high-level concepts which are important in change detection can be represented by a few visual words (tokens). A transformer encoder is used to model the input images into tokens. These tokens are converted to pixel-space for refining the original features using a transformer decoder.
- **CDMamba: Remote Sensing Image Change Detection with Mamba** [10] introduces CDMamba, a novel change detection model that integrates the strengths of Mamba architecture with CNNs to effectively handle both global and local feature extraction for remote sensing applications. The model addresses the limitation of traditional Mamba methods, which often overlook the importance of local details in dense prediction tasks.

3.2. Relevant on-board object detection methods

Papers about cloud, vessel and vehicle detection are presented.

- **Cloud detection on small satellites based on lightweight U-net and image compression** [11] explores the use of the U-Net model, originally designed for large biomedical images, by creating a lightweight adaptation suitable for on-board execution (L-Unet). Initially, a compression LeGall-5/3 wavelet transform is applied to the images to enhance the performance of the neural network and allow on-board execution. The results indicate L-Unet improved accuracy compared to other cloud classifiers, including L-Decov, Adaboost, Random Forest, and SVM.
- **BoatNet: automated small boat composition detection using deep learning on satellite imagery** [12] article is not explicitly focused on on-board execution. It performs ship detection using the YOLOv5l model, which is a lightweight version of YOLOv5. This model demonstrates very high detection precision and the ability to classify different types of boats.
- **Vehicle Detection Algorithm Based on Background Features Assistance in Remote Sensing Image** [13] proposes an algorithm based on the YOLOv4 [14] model, enhanced with a weight redistribution module that leverages feature

correlation. They applied a Gaussian kernel to the image dataset to reduce spatial resolution to approximately 1 meter, aiming for more realistic and generalizable data. The results indicate improvements over several state-of-the-art techniques, including SSD512, Faster R-CNN, FCOS, YOLT, YOLOv3, and YOLOv4.

3.3. Change detection datasets

This section lists change detection datasets, which are crucial for training the AI models used in the method to evaluate changes in image regions. Access to a large and diverse dataset is essential for effectively training AI models. Existing image datasets can be manipulated and adapted as needed; for instance, larger images can be split into smaller ones if required. Another important characteristic of satellite imagery is spatial resolution, which can be downsampled if the resolution in the dataset exceeds the required level.

In the analysis of the reviewed papers, a collection of datasets used for experiments in change detection was compiled. This information was further enhanced to create a comprehensive table detailing the relevant existing datasets and their availability for download. Table 1 is provided below.

Table 1: Overview of change detection datasets with their attributes sorted by published date.

Dataset	Publication Year	Image Pairs	Dimensions (pixels)	Bands	Image Type	Spatial resolution (m)	Shooting Time	Sensor	Scenario	Open Source
3DCD	2023	472	400 × 400	3	Multispectral	0.5	2022		Urban	☑
ChangeNet	2023	31000	1900 × 1200	3	Multispectral	0.3		World Imagery Wayback	Multiple	☑
Landsat-SCD	2022	8468	416 × 416	3	Multispectral	30	2022		Semantic changes	☑
S2Looking	2021	5000	1024 × 1024		Multispectral	0.5 to 0.8	2017, 2020		Rural	☑
LEVIR-CD+	2021	985	1024 × 1024	3	Multispectral	0.5	2002 to 2018	Google Earth	Multiple	☑
NASA Earth Observatory Change	2020				Multispectral			NASA	Multiple	☑
LEVIR-CD	2020	637	1024 × 1024	3	Multispectral	0.5	2020	Google Earth	Urban	☑
DSIFN	2020	394	512 × 512	3	Multispectral	2	2020	Google Earth	Urban, roads	☑
SECOND	2020	4662	512 × 512	3	Multispectral	3	2021	Multiple	Semantic changes	☑
Hi-UCD	2020	40800	512 × 512	3	Multispectral	0.1	2022		Semantic changes	☑
MIS-WH	2019		7200 × 6000	4	Multispectral (VHR)	1	2002, 2009	IKONOS satellite	Urban	☑
HRSCD Dataset	2019	291	10000 × 10000	3	Multispectral	0.5	2012, 2016	WorldView-2 satellite	Urban	☑
OSCD (Onera)	2018	24	600 × 600	3	Multispectral	10, 20, 60	2018	Sentinel-2 satellites	Urban, roads	☑
CDD (Season varying)	2018	16000	256 × 256	3	Multispectral	0.03–1	2018	Google Earth	Urban, roads	☑
WHU Building CD	2018	1	32507 × 15345	3	Multispectral	0.075	2018	QuickBird, WorldView, IKONOS, ZY-3	Urban	☑
GETNET	2018	2	463 × 241	198	Hyperspectral		2013		Multiple	☑
Hyperspectral Change Detection	2017		Multiple	224, 242	Hyperspectral		2004 to 2015	AVIRIS	Multiple	☑
Hermiston City	2017	1	307 × 241		Hyperspectral		2004	Hyperion	Urban	☑
Yellow River	2016		391 × 343		Heterogeneous		2008, 2010	Radarsat-2, Google Earth	Riverway	
Shuguang Village	2016		921 × 593		Heterogeneous		2008, 2012	Radarsat-2, QuickBird	Agricultural	
Hongqi Canal Dataset	2012		539 × 543	4	Multispectral	2	2013, 2015	WorldView-2 satellite	Riverway	☑
Minfeng Dataset	2012		651 × 461		Multispectral	0.5	2013, 2015	WorldView-2 satellite	Urban	
AICD	2011	1000	800 × 600	3	Multispectral	3	2011		Urban	
SZTAKI AirChange	2008	13	952 × 640		Multispectral	1.5	2000, 2005	FÖMI	Urban	☑

4. ANALYSIS

This section discusses the viability and projected performance of content-aware region-of-interest coding. It first presents a simplified proof-of-concept solution, followed by the definition of metrics to evaluate the technique’s performance and enable benchmark comparisons.

Without loss of generality, given a multispectral image of 4096 × 4096 pixels, the first step is to divide it into a grid of smaller 256 × 256 pixel cells. An AI model is then used to assess the probability of changes within each cell. Based on a defined threshold, cells with probabilities below the threshold are classified as “background” —indicating no significant changes— while those above the threshold are classified as “foreground.” Background cells are discarded, and only foreground cells are retained for compression using a lossless compressor (e.g., CCSDS 123.0-B-2 [15]) before transmission to the ground. A diagram of this process is shown in Figure 4. This straightforward approach enables the efficient discarding of uninteresting regions (background) in the image, significantly reducing the amount of data that needs to be processed and transmitted.

To develop an AI model for this task, the proposed path forward is to adapt deep learning architectures designed for object detection to output a value that quantifies the probability of changes in an image. This will involve modifying the last layer(s) of the neural network. Using pre-trained models can help accelerate and improve the accuracy of the solution. This proposal is based on the fact that object detection models are already capable of identifying objects in satellite imagery and discerning various regions within an image [16].

Figure 4: Example of an image divided into cells, with background cells discarded and foreground cells retained.

To evaluate the performance of this proof of concept or any future implementations, specific metrics must be defined. This is crucial for comparing different implementations and optimizing compression efficiency.

For example, given an AI model that achieves a target false negative rate (FNR) by adjusting the threshold determining whether a region contains changes, the corresponding false positive rate (FPR) and rate (bps) can be calculated based on the percentage of background area in the image (background rate, BR). Determining the rate is useful, as this metric is commonly used to evaluate the efficiency of compression techniques.

In the chart shown in Figure 5, multiple scenarios are presented for images with varying background proportions, along with the corresponding rate required to store them depending on the number of false positives—i.e., samples that are part of the background but not discarded. The chart demonstrates that even with a certain tolerance for false positives, the rate remains lower than that of applying a lossless compression technique. For comparison, the average compression ratio of 1.86:1 for CCSDS-123.0-B-2 lossless compression is derived from images processed during the commissioning phase of the Menut nanosatellite mission [17].

This suggests that if an AI model achieves a sufficient level of accuracy with a low false negative rate, this method can surpass traditional image compressors in terms of data reduction. It is important to note that rate can be further reduced, as the presented chart does not account for the subsequent compression of the selected regions.

Figure 5: Chart evaluating the increment of rate when the false positive rate (FPR) increases, sending more information than needed.

A metric to compare the performance of different content-aware region-of-interest coding techniques is essential. The false negative rate (FNR) can be calculated for specific rate values for a given image or averaged across a set of images. To compute these values, the threshold determining whether a region is foreground or background is incrementally adjusted from the minimum to the maximum. At each step, the resulting FNR and rate values are recorded, generating data points for comparison.

An example of this process is shown in Figure 6, where two techniques are compared, with the ratio of a lossless technique [15] included as a reference, indicating the point beyond which further compression is no longer beneficial.

The metrics presented allow for a thorough analysis of the feasibility of compression improvements and the ability to

Figure 6: Performance comparison between two content-aware region-of-interest coding, and a lossless technique.

determine which models perform better.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces a novel method for on-board satellite image compression: content-aware region-of-interest coding. The proposed approach employs deep learning to autonomously identify and segment areas of potential change within a single satellite image, eliminating the need for bi-temporal image comparisons. The innovation focuses on reducing the volume of data transmitted from satellites to Earth by compressing and transmitting only the most relevant regions of an image, and providing a generalized solution.

An exhaustive study of state-of-the-art techniques in change detection and on-board object detection was conducted. No techniques were found that resemble the generalized proposal of the presented method. Object detection techniques will be further studied in more detail to construct the AI model, while change detection techniques can be used to enhance the existing change detection datasets.

This work presents the method's step-by-step process, with a focus on the image segmentation phase. This approach significantly reduces on-board computational complexity by bypassing traditional change detection techniques that require two images and eliminating the need for computationally expensive image alignment processes. The initial proposed implementation suggested that the method can potentially reduce the amount of data transmitted while maintaining accuracy in detecting relevant image regions.

Future work will focus on constructing the AI model, improving its detection accuracy, and aiming for an on-board implementation. If successfully realized, this method could lead to more efficient data handling in satellite missions, particularly for small satellite remote sensing platforms.

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